

Mid-air haptic interface using a hybrid PMUT array

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Abstract. The covid crisis has highlighted the value of developing contactless systems. It has been already shown that a matrix of ultrasound transducers is able to generate haptic effects in the air. This is called mid-air haptic. In this paper, we report the development of a hybrid PMUT array built using an innovative “Piezo-in-flex” technology based on the integration of piezoceramic actuators on a polymer material. An electronic circuit has been designed and realized to provide the same signal to the 64 channels of the interface. Experiments showed the ability to obtain focalization points; with a promising acoustic pressure of about 120 Pa (136 dB) at 10 mm distance from the array, under 48 Vpp. Actuation signal is under optimization to generate a perceptible mid-air haptic effect in a close future.

Keywords: Mid-air, haptic interface, hybrid PMUT.

1 Introduction

Numerous applications require tactile interfaces today. In particular, many customers’ applications such as automotive, gaming, virtual reality, Smartphone or tablet PC can be concerned by high performances, low voltage haptic interfaces that allow the user to interact with his environment by the sense of touch. The COVID crisis has highlighted the need for developing contactless systems. A matrix of ultrasound (US) transducers is able to generate haptic effects without contact, in the air. This is called mid-air haptic. Some research groups have communicated about achieving mid-air haptic rendering [1, 2] and Ultraleap is marketing a development kit using this principle [3]. Nevertheless, all these developments use bulky magnetic transducers or time consuming and expensive silicon technologies, not always necessary to develop demonstrators. In this paper, we report the development of a hybrid PMUT array built using an innovative “Piezo-in-flex” technology based on the integration of piezoceramic actuators on a polymer material, in a cost effective way. Transducers are designed to operate at 31.3 kHz and an array of hybrid PMUT is assembled. Using an impedance meter, the resonant frequency is measured at 33 kHz, in good agreement with the simulated value. A driving electronic circuit has been developed to provide the same signal to the 64 channels of the array. Experimental study showed the ability to obtain focalization points; localized in the space, with a promising acoustic pressure of about 120 Pa (136 dB) at 10 mm

from the array, under 48 Vpp. Actuation is under optimization to generate a perceptible mid-air haptic effect in a close future.

2 Mid-air hybrid PMUT interface development

An innovative “piezo-in-flex” process able to build hybrid PMUTs using commercial piezoceramic actuators and a flexible polymer substrate was developed and presented in [4], which focuses on a single hybrid PMUT. The considered PMUT presents a diameter of 6 mm and consists in a Kapton piezoelectric patch glued on a 500 μm thick polycarbonate foil. Analytical calculation predicts a resonant frequency of 31.3 kHz for such component, integrated in a plastic packaging used to clamp each PMUT membrane on its periphery. The following Figure 1 gives a view of the main steps of the process and shows the new hybrid PMUT array. It consists in 256 PMUTs grouped by four transducers, leading to 64 independent PMUT channels.

Fig. 1. Main steps used to build the hybrid mid-air interface.

In order to actuate the hybrid PMUT array, a driving electronic circuit using a dedicated FPGA has been designed and realized. The challenge of the driving electronic circuit is to provide a similar signal in terms of intensity to all the channels and to adjust the phase shift between them to focalize their US emission at a specific point in space. In order to transmit the signal, each channel needs to be actuated by the adequate delay, and the signal pulse width. This width is given by the modulator table, here a tabulated sine common to all channels, multiplied by an apodization value (that represent the sine amplitude), for each channel. If the modulator table is hard-coded and can be modified only by a FPGA reconfiguration, delays and apodizations are reprogrammable via serial link. The driving electronics actuate the PMUT array with a sinusoidal signal presenting an amplitude of 48 V modulated at 200 Hz. Figure 2 gives the photography of the driving electronics of the PMUTs. The power stage boards (Figure 2a) translate the logic signal 0-3V from FPGA onto power signal 0-48V applied to the transducers. The matrix consists in four modules of 64 transducers grouped in patches of 4 transducers. Figure 2b shows the FPGA board aimed at driving the 64 groups of transducers.

Fig. 2. a) Power stage board. b) FPGA board.

3 Evaluation of the mid-air hybrid PMUT array

Before the assembly of the array on our acoustic bench, electrical impedances of the PMUTs are measured with an impedance analyzer (Keysight E4990A). The average resonant frequency is measured at 33 kHz, in good agreement with our modelization (an equivalent circuit formed by the vibrating membrane actuated with its piezoelectric actuator with the Butterworth Van Dyke model). The acoustic pressure is measured using a 4108 Brüel & Kjaer microphone, mounted on a 3D scanning bench, scanning the space in front of the array. The delays calculated and introduced on each PMUT groups by the electronic circuit allow focalizing the US waves on predefined points. 2D representations of measured pressures for different focused points are obtained. As evidenced by the Figure 3, we can move and control the focused point. However, in some case, unexpected high pressure points are obtained outside target point, which is currently investigated. A promising acoustic pressure of about 120 Pa (136 dB) at 10 mm from the array is measured on the focalization points under 48 Vpp. Actuation signal is under optimization to obtain a perceptible mid-air haptic effect in a close future.

Fig. 3. Pressure fields in front of the array with four different focalization points.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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